

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Tourism development and community business development through homestay in Panglipuran Village Bali

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Abstract

Homestay for the community is used as an additional livelihood after agriculture, therefore it needs in-depth research to find out more about the condition of homestay in Panglipuran Tourism Village. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the homestay business in Panglipuran Tourism Village seen from 3 (three main components of this business program, namely institutions, actors and products). The research method used in this research is a qualitative method with data collection methods in the form of in-depth interviews. The results of this study describe the homestay business program seen from local institutions as indicated by the existence of local organizations that regulate tourism activities, namely Pokdarwis Lingko` Cave. This organization oversees homestay business actors who are self-help communities in Panglipuran Tourism Village. This institution and homestay business actors produce products offered as attractions that are the reason for tourists to come in the form of homestays and activities that become tourist attractions. The results of this analysis are the basis for preparing recommendations for homestay businesses seen from these three components.

Keywords: Tourism; Panglipuran Tourism Village; Homestay business; Tourism Development; Community Business

1. Introduction

As time develops with the widespread definition of tourism, tourist destinations are also growing. One of the tourist destinations that is an alternative for tourists who are tired of the hustle and bustle of urban life and the decline in the quality of the city environment, is rural tourism or what is commonly called a tourist village. Tourism villages are formed by prioritizing the lifestyle and quality of life of the community and involving the local community by developing the quality of the village's products. Tourism villages are built with the concept of returning to nature and offering a more natural lifestyle by showing the authenticity of regional culture.

Therefore, various regions have begun to develop tourist villages as an alternative tourist destination offered to tourists, Bali's Penglipuran Village is one of them. Thanks to its cleanliness and neatness, this tourist village located in Bangli has also won several awards including Kalpataru, ISTA (Indonesia Sustainable Tourism Award) in 2017, and most recently, this destination was included in the Sustainable Destinations Top 100 by the Green Destinations Foundation.

In order for tourists to learn about the local culture, lifestyle, and economic industry, Panglipuran Tourism Village needs accommodation that can attract tourists to spend more time in the village. Therefore, the Panglipuran Tourism Village community is developing a Homestay business with the concept of experiencing the life of local people, where with this homestay, visitors can stay and interact with local people. Upon entering the village, visitors will already be greeted with rows of greenery. The more visitors enter the village area, the air and scenery will increasingly feel cool and

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beautiful with views of hedges that adorn the entire village area. When tourists visit this village, tourists are prohibited from using motorized vehicles. This is done to keep the environment of Penglipur Tourism Village free from pollution. Tourists can explore the uniqueness of Penglipur Village on foot. In addition, littering is also prohibited. In Penglipur Village, trash bins are provided every 30 meters.

Improving the welfare of the population through the presence of tourism will strengthen the economic resilience of the population while playing a role in improving the quality of the natural environment and conservation. This effort is one of the sustainable tourism development. The concept of tourism social entrepreneurship is known as tourism social entrepreneurship. Tourism social entrepreneurship can be interpreted as a social entrepreneurship activity in the field of tourism. Tourism social entrepreneurship is defined as people who carry out tourism business activities that inspire and encourage the activities of the surrounding community to participate in tourism business activities. Community participation and the implementation of tourism social entrepreneurship are inseparable from the indirect role of innovation. Innovation is needed to maintain products, both services and goods, so that they continue to be in demand by customers or consumers. Thus, to be able to survive and be competitive, every tourist village must innovate periodically. Innovation is the emergence of something new, which is different from before no matter how small it is. Innovation is a change, which previously did not exist, or that already exists to be even better. Tourism village innovation will continue to stimulate tourism villages to continue to be creative and make tourism villages more attractive. Research conducted by Divisekera and Nguyen (2018) which explains that it provides new insights into the role and effects of various inputs and related institutional factors that encourage innovation efforts by a community group. So it can be explained that sustainable tourism development efforts can be influenced by 3 factors, namely community participation, entrepreneurial activities and innovation. These three factors can be implemented in a Tourism Village. *Desa Wisata* includes a collection of communities, community activities in which there are innovations and creative things that can highlight the uniqueness of a Tourism Village.

In the concept of developing a tourist village with a focus on its economic aspects, local communities carry out entrepreneurial activities, the community builds a business based on innovation. Businesses run such as homestays, places to eat and provide souvenirs. The community itself is moved to do this with the aim of improving its economic level. The innovations that are carried out are adjusted to the current trend and the needs of tourists. However, the phenomenon that occurs from the implementation of entrepreneurial activities, the managers do not provide direct assistance to advance the entrepreneurial activities of the local community, so there are still many local people who have to work outside of the tourist village management to be able to get their economy. In addition to this, the sustainability of Penglipur tourism village based on sustainable tourism development must be able to provide benefits to the community so that the role of the community for the management of Penglipur tourism village can be maximally felt.

The three main components of homestay business development are expected to provide an overview of the condition of homestays in Penglipur Tourism Village. In terms of institutions, Penglipur Tourism Village has a *Pokdarwis* that functions to organize the course of tourism activities and collaborate with local government and the private sector that will help the community in developing homestay businesses. *Pokdarwis* also cannot run the activity program well if it is not assisted by self-help groups in Penglipur Tourism Village. Both of these components have products that are offered as tourist attractions of this village. The product will provide a description of the house used to stay and the activities that can be done while staying at the homestay. From the analysis, researchers can develop recommendations for homestay businesses seen from these three components, for better homestay business development in Penglipur Tourism Village.

2. Methods

The method used in this research is qualitative research method. According to Herdiansyah (2010), qualitative research has the essence of understanding. Understanding what is meant is understanding 'something' which can mean many things, for example understanding what other people feel, understanding the mindset and point of view of others, understanding a phenomenon based on the point of view of a group of people or a particular community with a natural setting which means research must be carried out directly at the location where the phenomenon occurs. This understanding is not determined in advance, but will emerge after analyzing the social reality that is the focus of the research. The use of this qualitative method is justified starting from the research objectives that want to analyze the condition of homestays as an effort to develop Penglipur Tourism Village, as well as the responses of tourists who have stayed in order to produce ideal homestay recommendations. From the research objectives, it is necessary to have an in-depth exploration of homestays, so that it can get an overview of homestays as the main accommodation that attracts tourist villages. The data collection techniques used were observation and in-depth interviews. The data

collected was then processed by reducing data, coding data, and grouping data into themes according to the objectives to be achieved.

3. Results and discussion

The research entitled Homestay as Business Development of Panglipuran Tourism Village Community obtained several results that will be explained in this section, namely Institutional, Actors, and homestay business development products in Panglipuran Tourism Village.

3.1. Institutionalization of Homestay Business Development in Panglipuran Tourism Village

Institutionalization of the village community is very important as a component of homestay development in Panglipuran Tourism Village. In this case, the institution is defined as a local organization that oversees tourism activities in this tourist destination.

3.2. Panglipuran Tourism Village Homestay Business Development Actors

In addition to the institutions that organize the activities in Panglipuran Tourism Village, homestay business actors are also an important component in the development of homestay businesses. Homestay business actors are those who directly run this business. In this section, we will discuss the Self-Help Groups that run the homestay program, specifically the Panglipuran Tourism Village Self-Help Group which is responsible for managing the homestay business in Panglipuran Tourism Village. These KSMs oversee homestay owners who have an important role in the homestay program development efforts.

3.3. Homestay Owners

Based on the analysis that has been conducted, researchers classify homestay businesses in Panglipuran Tourism Village into Wait and see participants. Homestay actors like this need to see in advance what the benefits of the homestay program are for them. This categorization is because during the research, researchers found samples of homestay owners who decided to join the program because of the benefits and advantages obtained by residents who had participated in the homestay program first. Therefore, the number of homestay owners has also increased since the program was first established. The homestay owners in Panglipuran Tourism Village cannot be called willing participants judging from the condition of the homestays through the researcher's analysis, for example, the majority of homestay houses do not even install the identification boards that have been given. and cannot also be classified as non-committing participants, because homestay owners still have a commitment to participating in this program. This can be seen from the fact that there are no homestay owners who have resigned from this program, even though until the time this research was conducted, not many tourists had joined the homestay program. As a wait and see participant, the Panglipuran Tourism Village community needs to see the benefits of the program before deciding to take part in the program. The benefits that can be felt by homestay owners and Panglipuran Tourism Village residents from this program can be seen through environmental, economic, and social aspects.

3.4. Homestay Business Development Products

Institutions and homestay business actors in Panglipuran Tourism Village must have a product produced. The product is an attraction for tourists to come and want to join the homestay program. In this product discussion, the product of the homestay business in Panglipuran Tourism Village will be divided into 2 types, namely the physical homestay house that is rented out to tourists and activities that become tourism attractions and the reason tourists visit and participate in this homestay business.

3.5. Homestay House Condition

The experience of a vacation in Bali with an overnight stay in Penglipuran Village Homestay will make an option for tourists who want to feel how to rest and communicate directly with the community, because the homestay that is built is located in each resident's house. With cleanliness and simple facilities, tourists can enjoy staying with a different atmosphere from a vacation by staying overnight at a hotel. Various designs of building types and facilities that appear to have been modified with shades of other Balinese Houses, and follow to make the standard facilities of a homestay in general, but most of the gates and kitchens still use the characteristics of Penglipuran Traditional Houses. The friendly and hospitable Penglipuran Village community will welcome and interact with serving with a sense of closeness, so that tourists will feel like staying at home. While staying at Penglipuran Village Homestay, some of the daily activities of the community can be witnessed, and if you feel bored in the room or in the homestay environment, a walk around the village whose environment is kept clean or a walk in the shady bamboo forest is an interesting choice. To stay for the

day, travelers need to pay IDR 375,000 per night and get breakfast. In addition, each bedroom is equipped with simple facilities according to the ability of the homestay owner, generally in the form of a small table, small chair, and small cupboard. However, the majority of houses used as homestays still combine the bathroom of the homestay owner with tourists, which can cause discomfort for tourists.

3.6. Panglipuran Tourism Village Homestay business activities.

Interaction between homestay owners and tourists Interaction with homestay owners is the main bridge for tourists to feel comfortable with the Tourism Village. Not infrequently in tourist villages, homestay owners where tourists stay become tour guides for these tourists. From the survey results that have been conducted on several homestay owners, the relationship between homestay owners who come is very close to tourists. The interaction between homestay owners and tourists is very good, especially with domestic tourists. If with foreign tourists, there are language barriers that cannot be reached by homestay owners, on the other hand, foreign tourists are also still unable to use Indonesian. Eating together is also one of the links between homeowners and tourists. Because when eating together usually both parties can tell each other, chat, and exchange ideas.

3.7. Local Attractions of Panglipuran Tourism Village

Penglipuran tourist village has people who live in Sudra caste equality, which makes their daily lives very peaceful. Travelers can deepen their knowledge of various ancient Balinese cultures, and even take a Balinese dance course. The Sacred Baris Dance is a rare dance that can be found in Penglipuran Traditional Village and serves as part of the Yadnya deity ceremony. Visitors can enjoy a performance of this dance accompanied by gamelan and supported by the Sekaa Gong Gede of the Traditional Village. The membership of the Sekaa Baris Sakral is regulated in the Awig-awig.

Penglipuran tourism village organizes various festivals that add to its tourism appeal. One of the festivals held here is the Penglipuran Village Festival (PVF) which packs a variety of achievements and features of this village. PVF is held every early December as part of a series of welcoming the new year. Various activities that can be enjoyed at PVF include the Parade of Balinese Traditional Clothing of the Past, Barong Ngelawang, Cultural Arts Parade, and various competitions. The organization of PVF is able to attract the attention of thousands of tourists every year. In addition to PVF, the Penglipuran community also often holds various ceremonies at certain traditional moments such as Ngaben, Jawa Semeton, Kajeng Kliwon Kuningan, Grainan Purnama, and others. Tourists can participate in enlivening the sacred but festive atmosphere of the ceremony.

3.8. Traditional Culinary

In Penglipuran Village there is also a unique culinary that must be tried, the names are loloh cemcem and tipat cantok. Loloh cemcem is a specialty drink made from cemcem leaves or kloncing leaves that is effective for digestion. This drink is also made traditionally and guaranteed not to use preservatives or artificial sweeteners. For food, Penglipuran Village has one mainstay menu, tipat cantok. This snack is a heavy meal consisting of ketupat and boiled vegetables which are then served together with peanut sauce. Not only that, tourists can also taste typical Penglipuran Village drinks made from water, plums and rock sugar. One of the typical drinks served in this village is Loloh Cemcem made from Cemcem leaves. It tastes uniquely like rujak, with a fresh sweet and sour flavor. The people of this village also produce traditional coffee that is famous for being delicious. The village's specialty is Mujair Nyat-Nyat, which is made from mujair fish seasoned like Ayam Betutu. It is served with edible flowers with a fresh sour taste.

3.9. Traditional Handicrafts

Cultural arts and souvenirs are an integral part of the charm of the secluded tourist village of Penglipuran. Here, trade is conducted in the courtyards of houses as the natives are prohibited from selling on the street. Tourists who want to buy or just look around, are welcome to enter the courtyards of residents' homes. A wide variety of souvenirs and art products are sold in people's homes, including handicrafts, farming, weaving and carving. These products are charming Balinese works of art. Shopping for souvenirs in Penglipuran Village is an unforgettable experience for tourists.

4. Conclusions

Homestay business developed by the community is one form of activity carried out in order to welcome foreign tourists visiting the village of Panglipuran Tourism Village. This is done because there is no special lodging available for tourists such as hotels, bungalows and other types of lodging. The number of homestays in the village of Panglipuran Tourism Village is still limited, therefore the community is developing a homestay business to anticipate the shortage of available rooms during the high season.

In developing a homestay business, there are 3 (three) main components that need to be considered by homestay developers, namely institutions, actors, and products. These three components must work together so that the homestay development business can run smoothly and become one of the reasons tourists come to visit Panglipuran Tourism Village.

Homestay owners in Panglipuran Tourism Village can be classified as wait and see participants. This is because the Panglipuran Tourism Village community needs to first see the benefits obtained by residents who have participated in this program before deciding to join. The benefits that can be felt can be seen environmentally, economically, and socially.

Products that attract tourists to come and stay at homestays are divided into 2 (two) types, namely homestay houses that are rented out to tourists and groups of tourists and activities that become tourist attractions as a reason for tourists to join the homestay program.

Traditional culinary packages are also one of the tourist products that are favored by many tourists. One type of culinary that is characteristic is that tourists can also taste typical Penglipuran Village drinks made from water, plums, and rock sugar. One of the typical drinks served in this village is Loloh Cemcem made from Cemcem leaves. It tastes uniquely like rujak, with a fresh sweet and sour flavor. The people of this village also produce traditional coffee that is famous for being delicious. The village's specialty is Mujair Nyat-Nyat, which is made from mujair fish seasoned like Ayam Betutu. The presentation is completed with edible flowers with a fresh sour taste.

Besides culinary packages, there are also other packages such as traditional handicrafts. A wide variety of souvenirs and art products are sold in people's homes, including handicrafts, farming, weaving and carving. These products are charming Balinese masterpieces. Shopping for souvenirs in Penglipuran Village is an unforgettable experience for tourists.

Panglipuran Tourism Village Homestay Program The village institution is the spearhead that drives the development of Panglipuran Tourism Village. Therefore, it is important for village institutions, both the village and community organizations, to hold the principle of community-based tourism development in Panglipuran Tourism Village.

As a tourist village, Panglipuran has been named the cleanest tourist village and must be kept clean. The overall drainage system must be kept clean so as not to cause odors. Cleanliness in the house must be considered, not only the rooms that are rented out as homestays but also other rooms that may be used by tourists staying overnight, for example the kitchen and living room.

The homestay program is not only related to the physical building of the house that can be used by tourists to stay. But also supporting activities that can be done when tourists stay at the homestay. This activity can be an activity offered to general tourists as well as groups that have their own activities. These tourism activities should be formed into tour packages offered to tourists who come to make it easier to find out the types of activities offered.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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